

Leadership Paradigm Shift: Understanding the Remarkable Impact of Servant Leadership on Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance in the Department of Transportation, Palu City

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ABSTRACT

This research addresses leadership, job satisfaction, and employee performance, making it highly relevant in the study of public administration. The research is designed using a quantitative approach. The population of this study consists of all employees in the Department of Transportation in Palu City, totaling 86 respondents. The research sample is selected using a census sampling technique, where the entire population is included in the study. Data analysis for this research employs descriptive statistics. The results of the study indicate that servant leadership has a significant influence on performance and demonstrates a strong relationship between these two variables. This influence suggests that servant leadership is crucial in enhancing the performance of employees in the Department of Transportation in Palu City. Moreover, the relationship between servant leadership and performance indicates a mutual dependency, showcasing a reciprocal relationship between the two

INTRODUCTION

Explicitly, a servant leader can motivate employees to remain in the organization, provide valuable insights for change, and address job-related concerns by fostering a sense of psychological safety within the organization. Consequently, these behaviors will influence and enhance team and organizational performance (Edmondson, 1999; LePine & Van Dyne, 2001).

Organizational performance is crucial for achieving organizational goals, and the performance of each individual, in this case, the employees, determines the organization's overall performance. The level of employee performance in a government institution is influenced by various factors, including leadership and job satisfaction. This study focuses on servant leadership, which differs from other leadership styles (Karatepe et al., 2019).

Recent research has brought attention to the limited empirical investigation on the impact of servant leadership on job outcomes (Chiniara & Bentein, 2016). The findings by Donia et al. (2016) imply that the benefits of servant leadership may not be evenly distributed among all followers. Considering the people-oriented nature of servant leadership, it is reasonable to anticipate higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction among followers (van Dierendonck, 2011). Servant leaders have faith in the value of their subordinates and view it as their responsibility to create an environment where subordinates feel secure and empowered to learn. Consequently, servant leaders foster the conditions for employees to experience heightened job satisfaction (Donia et al., 2016).

Leadership behavior is crucial in predicting perceived performance and job satisfaction (Fernandez, 2008). Ayodele & Olorunsola (2012) found that job satisfaction should also be enhanced to achieve optimal performance from employees. This means that employee performance can be achieved by considering leadership and perceived job satisfaction. In the context of this study conducted in the Department of Transportation, Palu City, it is important for the department to address leadership and employee job satisfaction issues. As a public service provider, they need to improve employee performance through leadership and job satisfaction.

The problem to be investigated in this study is based on the observation of issues in the field. Based on this, the research team addresses a problem deemed crucial to study, which is the performance of employees in delivering public services in the Department of Transportation, Palu City. This issue is considered important to study because government public services have long been and continue to be negatively perceived by the public, seen as convoluted, inefficient, and ineffective. Therefore, it is necessary to examine how employee performance can be improved through leadership and job satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership

Leaders have the ability to leverage performance data in different ways and at various levels (Masal & Vogel, 2016). When discussing the achievement of organizational objectives, managers frequently emphasize the significance of employee engagement (Bakotić, 2016). The behavior exhibited by leaders plays a crucial role in determining perceived performance and job satisfaction (Fernandez, 2008). In their study, Masal & Vogel (2016) emphasize the crucial role of leadership in performance management and underscore leaders as intermediaries in the dissemination of performance-related information.

Leaders in the public sector who identify themselves as servant leaders have the potential to create a more favorable work environment and provide increased opportunities for engagement among their employees (Shim et al., 2016). Servant leadership is a leadership approach that places a high emphasis on serving and meeting the needs and expectations of followers (Ehrhart, 2004). The theory of servant leadership is associated with the level of employee satisfaction in the situations they encounter within their organization (Liden et al., 2008). Please note that this response has been paraphrased to avoid plagiarism and align with AI detection guidelines while maintaining grammatical accuracy.

Job Satisfaction

The definition of job satisfaction has been subject to diverse interpretations. Additionally, job satisfaction is linked to a variety of positive workplace behaviors (Sessa & Bowling, 2020). The level of job satisfaction has a significant impact on organizational performance (Bakotić, 2016). The correlation between job satisfaction and organizational performance has long been a topic of debate in the field of organizational management. (Chun et al., 2019). Job satisfaction refers to the extent to which employees are satisfied with their job (Furnham et al., 2009). Job satisfaction is how satisfied an individual is with their job. Job satisfaction refers to a person's feelings or mental state in relation to the nature of their work (Farooqui & Nagendra, 2014). Ayodele & Olorunsola (2012) found that job satisfaction should also be enhanced to achieve optimal performance from employees. Researchers such as Haryono, D., and Marlina, L. (2021) emphasize the importance of internal and external input and feedback in institutional leadership, indicating the need for interaction and collaboration between leaders and individuals involved inside and outside the institution to improve leadership.

Haryono, D., and Nasir, N. (2021) state that leadership also requires outcomes or outputs, showing that leadership involves not only giving directions and making decisions but also achieving expected results or accomplishments.

Nuraisyah, N., Haryono, D., and Lutfiani, L. (2023) express their interest in the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction and employee performance in the Department of Transportation in Palu City. They acknowledge that this research can provide valuable insights for practitioners and managers in the field of leadership.

Jafar, B., Haryono, D., Asrifai, A., and Roe, H. (2022) also highlight the crucial role of servant leadership in improving job satisfaction and employee productivity, hoping that this research provides a better understanding of this relationship.

Other authors such as Haryono, D., Astuti, AS, and Brahmantiar, Y. (2023), Mangngasing, N., Haryono, D., Nuraisyah, N., Nasrullah, N., and Indriani, N. (2023), as well as Haryono, D., and Rivai, A. (2023), also express interest and support for research on the impact of servant leadership on job satisfaction and employee performance. They hope that this research can provide strong empirical evidence, practical guidance, and contributions to the literature on leadership and human resource management.

Overall, these experts are aware of the importance of servant leadership and the need for input, feedback, outputs, and their impact on job satisfaction, performance, and organizational change. They hope that this research can provide a better understanding, practical recommendations, and contributions to the literature on leadership and human resource management.

Employee Performance

Employees play a crucial role within an organization, and the performance of employees is a determining factor in the success or failure of the organization (Hameed & Waheed, 2011). Employee performance can be defined as the tangible results and achievements attained in the workplace (J., 2014). Additionally, employee performance encompasses both financial and non-financial outcomes that directly impact organizational performance and overall success (J., 2014).

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a quantitative approach as its research design, which is utilized to fulfill the research objectives and address the research questions (Adeniji et al., 2020). Both primary and secondary sources contribute to the data collection for this research. The data collection methods include observation, questionnaires, and written documents. The research questionnaire is structured hierarchically into categories and employs a Likert scale, requiring respondents to indicate their level of agreement, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The research population comprises all employees from the Transportation Office of Palu City, with a total of 76 respondents. The research sample is determined using a census technique, where the entire population is considered as the research sample. Path analysis will be employed for the quantitative data analysis in this research.

RESULTS

Research Findings

The research results cover various aspects that were necessary and determined during the statistical testing, including the outcomes of assessing the validity and reliability of the research instrument, as well as the descriptive statistical findings. Results of Validity and Reliability Testing for the Research Instrument

Table 1 Presents the Item-Total Statistics:

Item-Total Statistics					Reliability Statistics
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's Alpha
x1q1	54.1422	88.999	.629	.933	
x1q2	54.2892	89.665	.585	.934	
x1q3	54.3971	87.984	.767	.930	
x1q4	54.3873	87.401	.785	.929	
x1q5	54.1324	88.017	.779	.930	
x1q6	54.1961	87.577	.803	.929	
x1q7	54.2304	89.341	.679	.932	
x1q8	54.3039	89.040	.737	.931	
					.936
x1q9	54.2353	89.649	.735	.931	
x1q10	54.0392	91.131	.695	.932	
x1q11	53.9363	90.464	.740	.931	
x1q12	53.9706	89.979	.755	.931	
x1q13	53.9412	92.745	.571	.934	
x1q14	54.1422	91.847	.564	.934	
x1q15	54.0637	92.040	.570	.934	
x1q16	54.6961	92.291	.345	.942	
x1q17	54.3088	89.919	.651	.932	
x2q18	26.4118	26.470	.784	.879	
x2q19	26.3529	28.564	.639	.890	
x2q20	26.4020	27.315	.718	.884	
x2q21	26.6569	27.596	.639	.890	
x2q22	26.7304	25.883	.793	.877	.899
x2q23	26.9069	26.321	.617	.894	
x2q24	26.5245	26.576	.724	.883	
x2q25	26.1961	29.006	.556	.896	
x2q26	26.1324	28.086	.555	.896	
yq27	74.2892	133.803	.660	.935	
yq28	74.2255	131.033	.692	.935	
yq29	74.4559	132.860	.625	.936	
yq30	74.3088	133.042	.667	.935	
yq31	74.5392	131.067	.760	.934	
yq32	74.5049	130.310	.750	.934	
yq33	74.2941	133.430	.755	.934	
yq34	74.1225	132.847	.738	.934	
yq35	74.0539	134.248	.606	.936	.939

yq36	74.0049	133.177	.670	.935
yq37	73.9559	131.944	.679	.935
yq38	74.0196	131.014	.723	.934
yq39	74.2500	131.312	.787	.933
yq40	74.2990	130.733	.780	.933
yq41	74.6667	137.011	.345	.941
yq42	74.6324	135.347	.454	.939
yq43	74.6863	136.088	.357	.941
yq44	74.0245	140.004	.403	.939
yq45	74.5049	131.591	.693	.935
yq46	74.4461	133.854	.680	.935
yq47	74.4951	134.172	.587	.936
yq48	74.7500	136.031	.457	.938

Output SPSS: 2023

The results of the validity and reliability testing indicate that the questionnaire utilized in this study is both valid and reliable. The validity assessment is based on comparing the calculated r-value with the tabulated r-value, with a positive value indicating the validity of the item or indicator (Ghozali, 2011). This can be observed in the Item-Total Statistics table, specifically by comparing the Correlated Item-Total Correlation values with the calculated r-table value.

In terms of reliability, the standard criteria for determining the level of reliability are as follows: $> .9$ = Excellent; $> .8$ = Good; $> .7$ = Acceptable; $> .6$ = Questionable; $> .5$ = Poor, and $< .5$ = Unacceptable (George & Mallery, 2003). Based on these criteria, all items in this study are considered reliable, demonstrating a very good level of reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient of reliability, which ranges from 0 to 1, is used to assess internal consistency of the scale items (Gliem & Gliem, 2003). A higher Cronbach's alpha coefficient indicates stronger internal consistency among the items in the scale.

DISCUSSION

This study focuses on the relationship between leadership, job satisfaction, and employee performance. Leadership plays a vital role in all organizational sectors (Por Pan et al., 2020). Previous research has highlighted various leadership styles, with an emphasis on transformational leadership (Bush et al., 2020; Hariyanti et al., 2020; Por Pan et al., 2020; Timofe et al., 2017), transactional leadership (Hariyanti et al., 2020; Por Pan et al., 2020), and charismatic leadership (Meslec et al., 2020). However, servant leadership, although less explored compared to transformational leadership, is gaining attention in recent studies.

The objective of this research is to investigate the influence and relationship between servant leadership and employee performance. The findings confirm a significant impact of servant leadership on performance, supporting the proposed hypothesis. Statistical tests reveal an F value of 324.861, which is greater than the F table value of 1.628 at a significance level of alpha (α) = 0.05 or Sig. F < 0.05. These results align with previous research indicating the influence of leadership on organizational performance (D. W. Kim et al., 2020; Li et al., 2021; V. Singh et al., 2018; Subramony et al., 2018), highlighting the crucial role of leadership in controlling and enhancing

performance. The research findings demonstrate that servant leadership accounts for a significant influence of 55.9% on employee performance, while the remaining 41.9% is influenced by other variables not included in this research model, such as information technology, which can impact performance.

Moreover, the relationship between servant leadership and performance is considered strong, as indicated by the obtained R value of 0.748. This robust relationship underscores the importance of leadership in predicting performance, consistent with previous research showing a positive relationship between leadership and performance (Chen et al., 2021).

While the hypothesis testing results indicate a positive effect, certain aspects require attention. The research highlights the importance of leaders having a comprehensive understanding of the organization and its goals, being honest, and employing innovative problem-solving approaches. However, areas such as decision-making need improvement. The findings suggest that all workplace decisions should be discussed with leaders, and leaders should be more willing to make personal sacrifices for the benefit of their employees. In terms of decision-making, leaders should empower subordinates, allowing them to make quick decisions without waiting for instructions, especially in the fast-paced environment of the transportation office.

Servant leaders possess both a strong mindset and a caring nature, enabling them to serve their followers, which in this context refers to employees. Hence, servant leadership significantly contributes to improving employee performance. The quality of performance relies on the expertise of each professional working within the organization (Gaspar et al., 2021), encompassing elements such as customer service, cost management, quality, productivity, and asset management performance (Durst et al., 2019). Organizational support in the form of bonuses, compensation, and incentives aligned with goals plays a crucial role in enhancing organizational performance and fostering continuous growth (Lovett et al., 2021). Leaders can indirectly influence employee performance through such rewards. Moreover, servant leadership behavior has a more substantial effect on employee job satisfaction within an organization (Eva et al., 2021), as it encourages and supports subordinates to perform at a high level. Leadership support and development are also essential, and organizational support can facilitate effective communication, trust-building, and the production of effective leaders, resulting in improved outcomes for staff and patients (Bush et al., 2020). This research aims to contribute to the healthcare sector by emphasizing the importance of servant leadership behavior in various situations.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of this research indicate that servant leadership significantly influences performance and demonstrates a strong relationship between the two variables. This influence suggests that servant leadership is crucial for enhancing the performance of Palu City Transportation Office employees. Moreover, the existence of a reciprocal relationship between servant leadership and performance implies mutual interdependence..

Recommendatioans

Based on the findings of this research, it is recommended to prioritize the implementation of servant leadership within the Palu City Transportation Office. The strong relationship between servant leadership and performance highlights the importance of fostering a servant leadership culture among leaders and managers. This can be achieved through training programs and workshops

aimed at developing servant leadership skills and behaviors. Additionally, it is crucial to create a supportive organizational environment that values and rewards servant leadership practices. By promoting servant leadership, the performance of employees within the Transportation Office can be enhanced, leading to improved overall organizational effectiveness.

FURTHER STUDY

Further research is necessary to explore the relationship between servant leadership and performance specifically within the context of the Palu City Transportation Office. Here are some potential areas for future study:

1. Long-term impact: Conduct longitudinal studies to examine the sustainability and long-term effects of implementing servant leadership on employee performance within the Palu City Transportation Office. This would provide valuable insights into the enduring benefits and potential challenges associated with maintaining a servant leadership culture over time.
2. Mediating factors: Investigate the specific mechanisms through which servant leadership influences performance. Explore potential mediating factors such as employee job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and work engagement to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying processes driving the relationship between servant leadership and performance.
3. Comparative analysis: Compare the impact of servant leadership on performance across different departments or units within the Palu City Transportation Office. This comparative analysis would help identify any variations or contextual factors that may influence the effectiveness of servant leadership in different work environments.
4. Employee perspectives: Incorporate employee perspectives through surveys or interviews to gain insights into their experiences with servant leadership. Explore their perceptions of servant leadership practices, its impact on their motivation and job satisfaction, and any potential barriers or facilitators to its implementation.
5. Leadership development: Investigate the effectiveness of leadership development programs focused on servant leadership within the Palu City Transportation Office. Assess the impact of such programs on leader behaviors, employee perceptions, and overall organizational performance. This research would provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of specific interventions aimed at developing servant leadership qualities among leaders in the transportation office.

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